

TIKAS PAHINGA: LIVED EXPERIENCES OF ELEMENTARY SCOUTING THROUGH THE LENS OF LEARNERS

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Tikas Pahinga: Lived Experiences of Elementary Scouting through the Lens of Learners

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Abstract

The main objective of this qualitative study was to gain a comprehensive understanding of the experiences of elementary learners who participating scouting activities. Using purposive sampling band inclusion criteria, the participating fourteen (14) elementary learners from Maniki Central Elementary School, Kapalong Davao del Norte were identified. There were seven participated in in-depth interview and seven participated in focus group discussion. Utilizing thematic analysis, major findings uncovered meaningful insights into how elementary students perceive and experiences scouting, highlighting its positive impact on their personal and social growth. The results revealed the experiences of the participants were: challenges in terms of the environment while scouting; struggles as a scout leader; lack of financial support; and challenges and growth in scout activities. In response to the challenges that they have encountered, they supposed the following essential coping mechanisms: time management; being strong and motivated; teamwork and camaraderie; and self-discipline and goal setting. Upon reflecting on their entire experiences, they arrived at the following insights: being independent and responsible; social interaction and personal growth; learning fundamental life skills; and outdoor adventure and exploration. The results of this study were deemed significant by the participants, students, parents, teachers and researchers.

Keywords: *experiences, elementary learners, scouting participation, thematic analysis, qualitative research, Philippines*

Introduction

Scouting is a global movement with more than 50 million members spread over more than 200 nations and territories. It is the largest youth organization in the world, and its goal is to support people in achieving their full potential so that they can contribute positively to society. This is made feasible by the implementation of a non- formal education process that aids in the development of skills throughout life to create persons who are independent, supportive, accountable, and devoted. Although in some countries or territories, scouting is not necessarily related to academic activities, in some places, scouting is part of the extracurricular activities of elementary school (Jarialle, 2019).

In an international setting, specifically in Thailand, there are some challenges in managing the Scout Program in their school. It seems that scouting activities did not run well due to some schools felt that they were not able to carry out counseling, scouting, and physical education because of the shortage of specialized human resources and facilities in schools and the programs seem to be not implemented uniformly across the schools (Wangchuk, 2018).

Moreover, in the Philippines, among the top problems encountered by the learners who participate in scouting activities are dwell on the pupils' struggle with time management, short attention span, costly activities, and the difficulty of coping a tardiness. Additionally, younger participants may find it challenging to communicate effectively within the scouting framework Queroda et. al. (2020).

This research was important because there has been no study on the scout's current practices as well as to see the challenges behind it. The study is also significant since it can offer reliable data regarding how this beneficial program might be improved. On the other hand, scouting needs to focalize because it has intense problem to the elementary learners. In summary, the research problem in the proposed study focuses on understanding the lived experiences of elementary school students in scouting programs. Various stakeholders, including educational researchers, psychologists, scouting organizations, parents, and policymakers, may have a vested interest in this research to improve the quality of elementary education and extracurricular activities. Moreover, this study presented unique research that was examined and focused solely on the lived experiences of Elementary students in the context of scouting specifically on how they cope-up the certain challenges that they encounter, and what the impact of this scenario on their personal growth and development, character building, leadership skills and educational outcomes. The other studies which is "The Influence of the Scout Movement as a Free Time Option on Improving Academic Performance, Self-Esteem and Social Skills in Adolescents" by Ramon (2022) and "The Impact of Girl Scout Engineering Experiences on the Identity Development of Middle Schoolers" of Abigail (2022) that focuses only on the impact and the development of the youth but not considering the experiences and challenges that the learners encounter after the scouting program. Hence, my study is important and different because it depicts the depth of understanding and analyzing the lived experiences of elementary school learners who have participated in scouting programs. Depending on the specific focus, the research problem could delve into areas like the effectiveness of scouting in promoting certain skills or values among elementary students or the challenges they face in the context of scouting.

Finally, this study will enhance academic literature both within and outside the institution by disseminating its findings to research conferences and agencies, fostering scholarly interaction and the application of research insights. Consequently, the broader community will acknowledge its significance, leading to the formulation of actions and solutions for the discussed issues, and implementing the

recommendations provided.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the lived experiences of elementary school learners in the context of scouting. Moreover, this study sought to answer the following questions;

1. What are the lived experiences of elementary pupils regarding scouting participation?
2. How do the elementary pupils cope with the challenges faced in scouting?
3. What are the insights that the learners can share to their co-students regarding scouting participation?

Methodology

Research Design

A qualitative research approach was used in this study to better understand the participant's point of view. Qualitative researchers are the methodologies' intended audience. It made use of thorough and targeted research of small groups and individuals to aid and assist in the creation of a hypothesis. The information was gathered through observation, conversation, depiction, and interviews. This type of research also is dominated by naturalistic, interpretive, and inductive methodologies (Mayan, 2016).

In this context, the research design for this study was qualitative. It was to explore and understand the experiences of elementary learners in the context of scouting. By using this approach, I was able to collect the experiences, coping strategies, and insights of the key participants, which would not have been possible if I had used quantitative research methodologies.

In the meantime, I utilized phenomenology, which draws attention to and identifies phenomena from the perspectives of the actors involved in the circumstances. From a human perspective, this was typically understood to be the process of gathering in-depth data and perceptions using qualitative, inductive techniques like participant observation, interviews, and discussions, then presenting this from the perspectives of the research participants (Lune Berg, 2017).

In context, I employed phenomenology as it was greatly suitable for this academic endeavor. I realized the necessity to perform phenomenological research in the local context, given that my study solely attempts to account for the lived experiences of the elementary learners of Maniki, Central Elementary School who participated in scouting activities. Additionally, this study method allows me to delve further into the lives of the participants.

Participants

The participants of the study were composed of 14 Elementary Students of Central Maniki Elementary School. There were seven (7) participants for In-depth interviews and another seven (7) for focus-group Discussion. In this study, the participants were selected based on the following inclusion criteria: (a) they were bonafide students of Maniki Central Elementary School and (b) they were participants of different scouting activities for almost 1-3 years in that particular school and (c) they were Grade 5 and 6 students at the particular school.

Procedure

As a researcher, I went through a series of processes to gather data and other essential information for the study. Before starting the study, I sought advice from my adviser to determine how and what steps would be necessary to complete it. In this way, even before the study began, I planned ahead of time. I ensure that the data-gathering processes are conducted accurately to facilitate a smooth analysis and interpretation process. I made sure to establish contact with the individuals I intended to interview and confirm their availability. Initially, I went to seek permission to conduct research with a group of learners who participated in scouting programs, I informed them about the research. I need to communicate the purpose and goals of my study to the participants.

The participants got the chance to learn about the study's goal before the actual interviews. Interviews are the main data-gathering methods used in this qualitative study. Qualitative data collection techniques seek to offer insightful information on the underlying mechanisms and shifts in people's perspectives. To present the participants and request their agreement to participate in the study, it is crucial for me as the researcher to have an accurate understanding of the nature and goal of the research (Smith et al. 2013).

As a researcher, I made sure that the data gathered was related only to the experiences of elementary learners in the context of scouting. Thus, the researcher must have a one-on-one interview with the learners who participated in scouting programs. Also, ethical consideration and participation are properly adhered to in this research.

Data Analysis

The information gathered for the study was carefully structured and the researcher used technical resources to store data. The interaction is recorded using audio and video recorders. Qualitative analysis includes working with, grouping, and merging information into manageable pieces; synthesizing, looking for patterns; and debating what is relevant and what can be learned. To provide a more in-depth examination of the study, the researcher used a qualitative content analysis. By adopting a systematic and repeatable process,

content analysis entails the study of reaching conclusions about other states or attributes of the source from a text. Following the research analysis, it was discovered that every piece of information that was looked at came from a reliable source—the informants.

Thematic analysis and data reduction were used to comprehensively analyze the data analysis. On the one hand, a group of materials such as interview transcripts are frequently described using thematic analysis. The use of theme analysis in this study is advantageous since it enables one to infer information about the opinions of others, values, and knowledge from a collection of qualitative data (Caulfield, 2019).

In context, this study utilized thematic analysis to examine the gathered and acquired data. Finding any patterns that represent notions that the participants represent was the aim of the data collection phase. After that, the data was arranged logically into groups that summarize and make sense of the manuscript of the note. A comprehensive qualitative analytical technique called thematic analysis enables the researcher to extract new concepts and ideas from the data.

Moreover, thematic analysis was an advantageous approach to researching while looking to learn something about the views, opinions, backgrounds, experiences, and values shared by others from a collection of qualitative data, like survey answers, social media profiles, and transcripts of interviews. The application of theme analysis was flexible; the next phase in the research process and the goals of the study decide what to do with the themes once they have been identified. Theme analysis is a tool that many academics use to better comprehend their information and gain a deeper grasp of the content.

In addition, I finished the processes of getting familiarized with the data and producing initial codes, theme search, theme review, theme description, and verification, and bringing together the report. Transcription was the first step in the analysis process. Analyze it and divide it into pieces or components. It was an approach where the researcher tried to interpret the information that they had collected.

Finally, I listened to the recorded interviews of my participants and transcribed them to facilitate the coding process later on. I reviewed the data multiple times to familiarize myself with the responses and quickly identify the most common ones. I aggregated these common responses and derived a few themes, which I further refined to a select few. I employed data reduction techniques to eliminate irrelevant data and repurpose it as valuable study material for readers to understand. I sorted and organized a substantial amount of qualitative data, enabling me to integrate and categorize it efficiently. Data display techniques were utilized to present the data in matrices, charts, and graphs, allowing readers to draw their conclusions.

Ethical Considerations

The only goal of ethics in scientific investigations is to control both the participant and the researcher's situation. When gathering data from individuals, researchers must always abide by a set of ethical principles that serve as a guide for research designs and procedures. Human research typically aims to comprehend real-world events, investigate powerful remedies, examine behavior, and improve lives in various ways. When conducting research, ethical principles must be followed. These factors serve to sustain the validity of the research, promote academic or scientific integrity, and safeguard research participants' rights. As a result, different rules must be established to be followed to prevent ethical ramifications (Bhandari, 2022).

Respect for a person is an ethical principle that emphasizes consideration and appreciation for others' natural autonomy and shows respect for them. The idea of autonomy can be protected by providing participants with adequate information about the nature and goal of this research study in the participant's information leaflet in an understandable way to improve their informed consent (Kalu and Bwalya 2017).

For the participants in this study, an informed consent form was prepared in advance. Participants may learn more about the study by filling out the form, which gives comprehensive information about it. The researcher respected the participants' viewpoints and opinions throughout the interviews. Establishing a respectful relationship with the participants is essential, as it will take into account their beliefs, cultures, and way of life and offer them the option of participating or not. The subjects are always treated with respect because the study came after their significance. The researcher obtained consent to record the entire interview, including the participants' comments, before each one. The participants are also notified of their rights to receive information about the study's findings.

Consent is formalized in order to protect people's right to choose whether or not to engage in the research, and to foster research interactions that are built on "trust and integrity." It is crucial that a person's decision to participate in the research is voluntary and will be based on accurate knowledge about the implications of their involvement and ensuring the validity of consent is a fundamental requirement in the past (Klykken, 2021).

In this study, participants were given informed consent ahead of time before the set date for In-depth interview. The participants were asked for their vacant time and a preferred place for them to comfortably answer to give their opinions, insights, and thoughts about my study. In this case, after conducting an interview, the participants were eventually notified of the results and findings of the given interview.

Confidentiality refers to the researcher's obligations to protect the information entrusted to them. A breach of confidentiality could have had serious consequences if other stakeholders had been able to identify the participants. It was also important to establish trusting

relationships with the participants (Tremblay and Cadieux 2018).

In context, it is crucial to consider the discoveries and studies, as well as the safety of participants. The identities of the participants are kept secret. All materials, including videotapes, encrypted transcripts, notes, and other artifacts, shall be destroyed after the data has been analyzed. Some of the informants were cautious to participate in the interview at first because they didn't know what to say, but when I reassured them that their comments would remain private, they gave me the chance to appear at ease when responding to the interview questions. The questions are being asked with greater caution, and this research has been respected.

Justice requires reasonable allocation of the risks and benefits as the results of the study. Therefore, acknowledging the contribution of all the participants shall be highlighted as they become an integral part of the success of this study. They should be given due credit in all their endeavors (Boyce and Neale 2006). In this study, the researcher prepared a necessary amount for the snacks to offer and accommodated them properly.

To ensure justice, the participants were not required to spend any amount of money as their contribution to the research was acknowledged. The researcher recognized the importance of all participants and credited them for their valuable contributions to the study. Their efforts were fully appreciated, and as a gesture of gratitude, practical tokens were provided to express appreciation for their involvement in the research.

Results and Discussion

Participants

The participants of the study were the elementary students of Central Maniki Elementary School. They were all in grade 5 and grade 6 and had been participating in scouting for almost 1-3 years. There were fourteen (14) elementary students involved in the study: ten (10) females and four (4) males.

The in-depth interview and focus group discussion were conducted face-to-face inside the campus of Maniki Central Elementary School via audio recording. The researcher asked the participants if they wanted to be interviewed. The researcher got what she wanted and both the interviewer and interviewee were pleased with the result, resulting in a seamless flow and open communication whenever extra or probing questions were required. The participants were given the choice to refuse to respond to any question they considered unbeneficial or in opposition to their wishes. To ensure confidentiality, the information or data collected during the interviews was treated with the utmost confidentiality. Only the researcher and the participants had access to this information, which was shared verbally but not included in the study due to its nature.

Table 1. *Participants of the Study*

<i>In-depth interviews (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Code</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Gender</i>
Lovely	IDI-01	10	Female
Pretty	IDI-02	11	Female
Polka	IDI-03	10	Female
Straight	IDI-04	12	Female
Kulot	IDI-05	11	Female
Cat	IDI-06	10	Female
Rosas	IDI-07	10	Female
Total= 7			
<i>Focus group discussion (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Code</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Gender</i>
Geyb	FGD-01	11	Female
Happy	FGD-02	11	Female
Handsome	FGD-03	12	Male
Slang	FGD-04	11	Female
Yeesha	FGD-05	11	Male
AJ	FGD-06	11	Male
Monalisa	FGD-07	13	Male
Total= 7			

To adhere to the data collection process, the researcher used smartphones to record the participants' responses during the interview. Additionally, the researcher requested permission from all the participants to record the entire conversation during the interview, and they all politely agreed. All participants were accommodating and comprehended the request, except for one condition: that their identities remain anonymous in the study.

All participants in each case were given pseudonyms to protect the identities of all the participants. Pseudonyms were also given to each participant to protect their identity as well. For instance, in my in-depth interview session, Ms. Straight was given the name of the participants who had straight and shiny hair, while Ms. Kulot was the name given to the participants who had beautiful curly hair.

Lovely was named to the participant who is loving to the people she talked to, and Ms. Pretty was the name given to the participant who looks fresh and has a pretty face. Ms. Rosas was named to the participant because that is her favorite flower, while Ms. Cat was given to the participant because that is her favorite pet, and she likes to take care of it. Ms. Polka was named given to the participant who dressed in polka dots polo during the interview session.

Also, in my focus group discussion, Ms. Yeesha was named given to the participant because she idolized Yeesha in the movie marathon that she watched before, while Mr. Handsome was named given to the participant who looked handsome during the interview. Mr. Happy was named given to the participant who always has a smiling face, while Ms. AJ was named given to the participant because she likes AJ's name. Mr. Slang was named among the participants who can speak fluent English language during our interview session, while Ms. Monalisa was given to the participant because she looks like Monalisa in the movie. Lastly, Mr. Geyb was named given to the participants who always say a "geyb" in his expressions.

Categorization of Data

After the interview, the recorded conversations were transcribed, translated, and subsequently analyzed. The researcher initiated the analysis through the process of coding. Coding was the technique of arranging resources into pieces of text before giving meaning to the information. The coding technique was utilized to provide a description of the set of people as well as the categories of themes to be analyzed. These topics were used to help form a broad description of the phenomena under investigation. Data results were presented in the form of a table. The data gathered was handed to the data analyst for analysis of data and emerging themes.

The data was categorized into central themes based on the research questions, and these themes were presented. Thorough discussions were conducted to vividly describe the themes from the study, while the core ideas of the participants' responses were also included in the table alongside the major themes.

To add trustworthiness to the study, the researcher made note of the dimensions of credibility and transferability. To address credibility, member verification was carried out in addition to the triangulation approach. This was accomplished by providing copies of the interview transcript to participants so they may remark on it and certify its authenticity.

Regarding transferability, the researcher said right away that the results were not generally applicable since these views were solely based on the personal experiences of the participants in the particular school.

Research Question No. 1: What are the lived experiences of elementary pupils regarding scouting participation?

This question aimed to explore and understand the lived experiences of elementary learners regarding their scouting participation for almost 1-3 years. It sought to uncover the challenges, successes, and journeys of these students as they navigate their 1-3 years of in participating scouting activities. In the responses of the participants, there were three emerging themes that the researcher has found. The following themes are; challenges in terms of the environment while scouting; struggles as a scout leader; lack of financial support; and challenges and personal growth in scout activities.

Challenges in terms of the Environment while Scouting

Scouting activities often involve exploring natural environments, camping, hiking, and engaging in outdoor adventures. But behind every outdoor activity, students struggle to adapt and adjust to their new environment. According to some of the participants, they struggled to face new challenges especially in dealing with and being with other students because of fears and curiosity. These challenges presented a unique demand resilience, adaptability, and willingness for the learners to learn and grow. These challenges create a unique demand for their resilience, adaptability, and willingness to step outside their comfort zones. As they navigate to new environments and experiences, they learn to cope with their fears and develop the courage to engage with their peers. This process encourages them to find creative solutions to overcome obstacles and fosters a sense of camaraderie as they support one another.

Table 2. *The Lived Experiences of Elementary Pupils Regarding Scouting Participation*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Challenges in terms of the Environment while Scouting	There are times that the place where the cameral happened lacks some resources like water and CR/Comfort rooms. Also, I found it difficult to adapt to the new environment since I will talk and be friends with other students from other schools." - IDI-05 Last year during our scouting in Tagum City, I got sick and had a cough and cold. That is why it is hard for me to join different activities that time to represent our groups." - FGD-02 "It will be difficult for me to adjust to my new friends because some of them have a bad attitude." - IDI-01 There are times that we have misunderstandings with my friends but I limit and manage my emotions so that the fight does not get worse."- IDI-01
Struggles as a Scout Leader	"The struggle that I encounter in scouting is on how to manage my scout members and the proper way to practice the funsedrill activity since some of them didn't cooperate well." – FGD-03 "For me, I am one of the leaders of our group yells then every time we have practice, I find it difficult to manage my time since I am a journalist member of our school, and it is hard for me to manage my group as well." – IDI-02 "My struggle as a leader of boy scout is that my members didn't listen when I gave my instructions that is why I

Lack of Financial Support	<p>give them punishment which is push-ups and others.” – FGD-05</p> <p>Financial problem is not easy when you have to join scouting because there is a lot to pay when you join girl scout especially when the camp will be held out of our school campus.” – IDI-03</p> <p>I’m struggling with a lack of financial support for our camporal events because sometimes I have only a short amount of allowance, and we have a hard time finding money to pay but then I thank my parents for finding a way just so I can join scouting.” - FGD-07</p>
Challenges and Growth in Scout Activities	<p>It’s difficult for me to join scouting when there are a lot of obligations that need money. Like you need to wear a girl scout uniform, which is very expensive, and the allowance I need for how many days.” - FGD-06</p> <p>“The struggles I went through as a girl scout was waking up early because at 2:00 am I need to wake up to shower, to prepare and eat breakfast.” - IDI-07</p> <p>I cannot wake up early in the morning and my groups cannot cooperate well in any group activities that we have.” - FGD-04</p> <p>“Last year, when I joined scouting, I got sick and I struggled with how to properly lead my members and companions because it was my first time becoming a leader.” - FGD-01</p>

Ms. Kulot (pseudonym) candidly shared her experience during her participation in scouting wherein she struggled to adapt to the new environment there because of a lack of resources in the place where the camporal happened. She also revealed how difficult it is for her side as a timid person to socialize with other students since she needs to be with them as part of her scouting journey. She said that:

“Naay usahay nga ang lugar kung ang camporal mahitabo kay gamay ra ug tubig ug cr pariha anang maligo mi pero gamay ra ug tubig, then maglisod pud ko ug adapt sa akong new environment kay lahi nasad akong makauban ug makaila gikan sa lain laing schools.” (IDI-05)

(There are times that the place where the camporal happened lacks some resources like water and CR/Comfort rooms. Also, I found it difficult to adapt to the new environment since I would talk and be friends with other students from other schools.)

Similarly, Ms. Happy (pseudonym) shared her struggle during her participation with a sorrowful moment and worried with their groups. It leads them to despair their groups to continue in participating different activities. Her statement serves as a reminder that scouting is not just the destination of activities itself but also about the journey and the challenges faced along the way. She said that:

“Last year kay gikalintura ko, sa Tagum mi ato na time and gi ubo ug gi sip-on ko that’s why maglisod ko ug apil sa mga activities nga mag presentar para sa amoang grupo.” (FGD-02)

(Last year during our scouting in Tagum City, I got sick and I had a cough and cold. That is why it’s hard for me to join different activities at that time to represent our groups.)

In addition, Ms. Lovely (pseudonym) confessed her own experience with low confidence that she struggled to adjust to the mood swings of her new friends since they have different attitudes which she perceives as challenging to deal with. In this idea, she highlighted the importance of positive socialization, mutual respect, and the impact of negative attitudes on every individual within a scouting community. She said that:

“Maglisod ko ug adjust sa mga makaila nako nga mga new friends, kay naa man jud uban nga mga maldita ug maot ug batasan.” (IDI-01)

(It will be difficult for me to adjust to my new friends because some of them are cursed and have a bad attitude.)

Moreover, Ms. Lovely (pseudonym) shared her difficulties encountered specifically in handling friendship conflicts and managing connections with others. She addressed having miscommunications with her peers but emphasized that she tries to keep her emotions in control to keep things from getting worse. Her peaceful resolution demonstrates resilience and maturity as she goes through with scouting activities. She said that:

“Naay times nga maglalis mi sa akong mga friends pero gina limit ug manage gihapon nako akong emotion para dili mo dako ang away” (IDI-01)

(There are times that we have misunderstandings with my friends, but I limit and manage my emotions so that the fight does not get worse.)

Struggles as a Scout Leader

In participating in scouting activities, the elementary learners expressed their thoughts about the struggles that they encountered in terms of the different responsibilities that they have as a scout leader. Looking forward to the stories of Mr. Handsome and Mr. Geyb as the leaders of Boy Scouts, they shared that they struggled to manage their diverse group members. Amidst the badges and outdoor adventures, these young scouts often encounter challenges in understanding and embodying concepts like leadership and responsibility.

Mr. Handsome (pseudonym) highlighted his struggles based on his own experiences as a leader that he finds difficulties in terms of managing his group members. From organizing activities to fostering teamwork and discipline, he struggled to handle and maintain

peace among diverse individuals in a group. He said that:

“Ang struggle nako sa scouting kay kung unsaon nako pag manage sa akong mga scout members ug tarong nga pag practice sa funsedrill kay ang uban is dili mag cooperate ug tarong.” (FGD-03)

(The struggles that I encounter are on how to manage my scout members and the proper way to practice funsedrill activity since some of them did not cooperate well.)

Similarly, Mr. Geyb (pseudonym) also shared his thoughts about his own experience as a leader of Boy Scouts. Leading a group of Boy Scouts has been a journey filled with struggles, so he implements disciplinary actions and rules such as push-ups and other punishments to ensure compliance and maintain order within the group. He said that:

“Ang akong struggle sa pagka leader nako sa boy scout kay akong mga kauban dili maminaw sa akoang instructions mao ng naa silay mga punishment nga push up ug uban pa.” (FGD-01)

(My struggle as a leader of Boy Scouts is that my members did not listen when I gave my instructions which is why I gave them punishment which is push-ups and others.)

In addition, balancing multiple leadership roles can be a demanding task, as seen in the response of Mrs. Pretty (pseudonym) who serves as a leader in their group while also being a journalist in their school. Her challenge arises from the conflicting demands on her time and energy, particularly during practice sessions where effective management becomes crucial. She stated that:

“Leader man ko sa among group yells then everytime naa mi practice kay maglisod ko unsaon nako kay journalist man sad ko and every afternoon is naga journal mi at the same time mag practice pud para sa among yells then maglisod ko sap ag manage sa akong grupo.” (IDI-02)

(I am one of the leaders of our group then every time we have practice, I find it difficult to manage my time since I am also a journalist member of our school, and it’s hard for me to manage my groups as well.)

Lack of Financial Support

As I delved into the experiences shared by the elementary learners, they shared insight and realized that even how happy they were in scouting, they struggled with financial support for them to participate and enjoy the scouts. This kind of struggle not only dampens the enthusiasm of scouts but also deprives them of valuable learning opportunities that shape their character and skills. Moreover, these financial challenges lead the young scouts to feelings of exclusion and frustration, making it harder for them to engage with their peers and fully immerse themselves in the scouting community.

Ms. Polka (pseudonym) reflects on the financial challenges she faces in participating in the scouting program. She expresses how difficult it is to be involved when money is tight, as the program often requires various fees, especially for activities for off-campus camping trips. Her struggle underscores the burden of costs associated with scouting. These financial pressures make it hard for her and others in similar situations to fully participate and enjoy the benefits of scouting, despite their interest and commitment. She stated that:

“Financial problem ang akong problema sa pag apil sa scouting kay daghan kaayo ug bayrunon labi na kung didto mo sa layo mag scouting.” (IDI-03)

(Having a financial problem is not easy when you have to join scouting because there are a lot of fees that we need to pay especially when the camp will be held outside the school campus.)

Additionally, Ms. Monalisa (pseudonym) shared her experience that reflects her challenges related to financial limitations. She mentions the difficulties they face in providing for camporal events because of her limited allowance. Nevertheless, she thanks her parents for continuing to encourage and support her just to participate in scouting despite their financial challenges. This emphasized how crucial parental guidance and ingenuity are in helping pupils to participate in different extra-curricular activities like scouting. She mentioned that:

“Nag struggle ko kay kulang sa kwarta nga madala sa among camporal kay usahay gamay ra akong allowance, maglisod mi ug asa manguhag kwarta ibayad then pasalamat ko kay mapangitaan ug paraan sa akong parents’ para lang maka join ko sa girl scout.” (FGD-07)

(My struggles are due to lack of money to bring in our camporal events because sometimes I have a short amount of allowance, we have a hard time finding money to pay but then I thank my parents for finding a way just so I can join scouting.)

Furthermore, Ms. Pretty (pseudonym) illustrated her challenges in managing multiple responsibilities. As a leader of her scouting group, she feels the pressure during practices. Additionally, she faces difficulties in time management because she is also a journalist at their school. So, balancing these roles makes it hard for her to effectively manage both journalist and scouting activities. She stated that:

“Leader man ko sa among group yells then everytime naa mi practice kay maglisod ko unsaon pag manage sa oras kay journalist man sad ko and every afternoon is naga journal mi at the same time mag practice pud sa among yells, maglisod pud ko sa pag manage sa akong grupo.” (IDI-02)

(I am one of the leaders of our group then every time we have practice, it feels difficult to manage my time since I am a journalist member of our school, and it is hard for me to manage my groups as well.)

Challenges and Personal Growth in Scout Activities

Participating in scout activities presents a range of challenges that test the resilience and adaptability of the learners. One of the common struggles faced by learners is the requirement to wake up early. This is a simple yet significant challenge that highlights the difficulty in adjusting to a disciplined schedule. Moreover, as one learner mentioned the issue of group cooperation will add another layer of complexity to their scouting experience. We all know that successful scouting activities rely heavily on teamwork, communication, and mutual support. When a group struggles to cooperate, it affects the overall effectiveness and enjoyment of the activities. This challenge requires them to develop essential social skills and leadership skills. By navigating these hurdles, learners gain resilience, discipline, and teamwork which are essential attributes that extend far beyond their scouting experiences.

Ms. Rosas (pseudonym) straightly shared her experiences during scouting and she mentioned that waking up at 2:00 am to shower, prepare, and eat breakfast showcases her dedication to the responsibilities and demands of being a girl scout. This situation demonstrates her perseverance and determination to work hard in her duty as a scout, demonstrating her commitment to fulfilling the obligations and challenges offered by scouting. Additionally, she highlights the significance of prioritization and time management that scouting seeks to teach to its scouts. She said that:

“Ang struggles nga naagian nako sa girl scout kay magsayo og mata kay 2:00 am dapat magmata na para maligo, mag prepare ug magkaon.” (IDI-07)

(The struggle I went through as a Girl Scout was waking up early because at 2:00 am I needed to wake up to shower, prepare, and eat breakfast.)

Similarly, Mr. Slang (pseudonym) highlighted two significant struggles he faced during his participation in scouting: difficulty waking up early in the morning and a lack of cooperation within his groups during activities. His difficulties highlighted how crucial it is to address cooperation, time management, and discipline in the scouting environment. These difficulties offer chances for development and learning, highlighting how important it is to have certain abilities to improve both personal growth and the scouting experience. He confessed that:

“I cannot wake up early in the morning and my groups cannot cooperate well in any group activities that we have.” (FGD-04)

In addition, Mr. AJ (pseudonym) indicated the various difficulties he encountered while taking part in scouting. At first, he had trouble getting out of nap early, which suggested that he had trouble with discipline and organizing his time which are crucial for scouting. He also had problems with interpersonal interactions when participating in activities, which brought to light difficulties with cooperation, communication, and teamwork within his scouting groups. He indicated that:

“Pag apil nako last year ug scouting kay nagkasakit ko then maglisod ko unsaon pag lead ug tarong sa akong mga member ug kaubanan kay first time pa nako nahimong leader ato.” (FGD-06)

(Last year, when I joined scouting, I got sick and I struggled with how to properly lead my members and companions because it was my first time becoming a leader)

Research Question No. 2: How do the elementary pupils cope with the challenges faced in scouting.

This question focused on understanding the strategies, techniques, and coping mechanisms by the elementary pupils to conquer the different challenges they encountered during their participation in the scouting program. It explored how these students navigate some obstacles in scouting for them to be encouraged and positively face different activities despite of many challenges that they have. This question aimed to uncover the various techniques that the learners utilized to overcome different challenges they faced. The following themes were: time management; being strong and motivated; teamwork and camaraderie; and self-discipline and goal setting.

Table 3. Coping Mechanism of the Elementary Pupils in Participating Scouting Program

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Time Management	I have always set my schedule every day and I will do first the most important things like doing my academic responsibility before having a practice with our scouting activities.” - IDI-05. Balance everything. There is a need for me to balance my academic responsibilities and scouting activities for me to not feel pressure.” - FGD-05 “I learned time management from my sporting coach, and I applied it to my scouting activities and my academic responsibilities to make it balance and no one will behind” - FGD-04 “Time management and it is important to set a schedule every day. For example, you have to do your projects and assignments in the morning and practice dancing in the afternoon” - IDI- 01

	<p>"I prefer to do first those in priority. I set and arrange my schedule every day for me to not feel pressure and not have any conflicts." - IDI-06</p> <p>"I set a schedule for my academics and scouting so that both are balanced and I cannot neglect any workloads."- FGD-06</p>
Being Strong and Motivated	<p>"I always think positive, smile and always remind myself that I can do it despite many challenges that we have." - IDI-01</p> <p>"I always pray and stay motivated, then always kind to others especially to my teachers and to the elders." - IDI-04</p> <p>"I always smile and stay humble at all times. I did not mind any problem that we had instead, I always prayed to God, and I always motivated myself that I can do it all."- IDI-05</p> <p>"As being one of the motivations to my group, even from the one who struggles, I will lead them to be positive and motivated by just enjoying our life and always pray."- FGD-04</p>
Teamwork and Camaraderie	<p>"I feel happy and enjoy since we can finish our work earlier and getting to know each other to work together is better since we have learned a lot from each other." - FGD-04</p> <p>"I feel happy and blessed when I am with my friends because we can help each other to solve the problems that we have."- IDI-06</p> <p>"The most interesting thing I have learned is that you can freely enjoy your life even with a small thing around."- IDI-01</p> <p>"I am so blessed with my friends because I can freely ask for help and we can easily solve our problems."- IDI-02</p> <p>"I'm happy to be with my friends because I learned a lot from them, we also can bond and share our problems." - FGD-07</p>
Self-discipline and Goal Setting	<p>"Based on my struggles with financial shortages, my techniques are to save money in my piggy bank so that by the time comes, I have enough to pay. I also have another struggle where being late results in a punishment. To avoid this situation, I wake up early so I won't be punished." – FGD-01</p> <p>"Since my problem is waking up early, my technique is to practice going to bed early at night and waking up early in the morning." - IDI-01</p> <p>"My technique is to stay strong, set a schedule for tasks, and always prioritize the most important ones first." – IDI-02</p> <p>"For me to overcome my struggles which is hard to wake up in the morning then maybe, I will practice myself to wake up early and doing an exercise." – FGD-04</p>

Time Management

Time management is an essential coping mechanism for elementary learners in scouting. These young scouts juggle schoolwork, scouting activities, family time, and other hobbies, which can be overwhelming without proper organization. By developing effective time management skills, they can balance their responsibilities more efficiently, reduce stress, and fully enjoy their scouting experience. With structured schedules, these young scouts learn to allocate time for homework, training, and family commitments, which fosters a sense of responsibility and discipline.

Ms. Kulot (pseudonym) reflected on her strategy of portraying time management as a coping mechanism for actively participating in Girl Scouts. She shows a disciplined and organized attitude to time management by putting her academic obligations first to her scouting activities. With this strategy, she can complete her academic obligations without sacrificing her involvement in scouting. She said that:

"Gina set nako akong schedule and gina una nako ang mga mas importante nga mga buluhaton pariha anang unahon ang mga academic responsibilities then paghuman kay mag practice nako para sa among mga group activities". (IDI-05)

(I have always set my schedule every day and I will do the most important things like doing my academic responsibility first before having a practice with our scouting activities.)

In addition, Ms. Yeesha (pseudonym) also acknowledged the necessity of balancing academic responsibilities and scouting activities to avoid feeling overwhelmed and pressured. Through efficient time management and a balanced allocation of her time between these activities, Ms. Yeesha can stay in control while bearing less stress, which will enable her to achieve academic and scouting success without sacrificing either. She stated that:

"E balance tanan buhatunon. Dapat balance tanan buhatunon nako sa school og sa scouting para dili ko malibog" (FGD-05)

(Balance everything. There is a need for me to balance my academic responsibilities and scouting activities so I do not feel pressure.)

Mr. Slang (pseudonym) also treasured the knowledge and skills that he learned from his sporting coach and reflected on the importance of utilizing time management in every aspect of our responsibilities. He applies his knowledge which helps him to stay organized, and efficient, and ensures that he can keep up with his responsibilities without falling behind in any aspect of his life. He said that:

"I learned time management from my sporting coach and I applied it to my scouting activities and my academic responsibilities to make it balance and no one will behind." (FGD-04)

(I learned time management from my sporting coach, and I applied it to my scouting activities and my academic responsibilities to make it balanced so no one will be behind.)

In response, Ms. Lovely (pseudonym) highlighted the significance of time management as the guide and best strategy for in

participating different extra-curricular activities like scouting. She highlights how important it is to create a daily routine that allows time for various activities. This strategy encourages her to promote efficiency and productivity by assisting and maintaining a balance between her scouting duties and her interests and obligations. She said that:

Time management and dapat naka schedule na imuhang buhaton adlaw². Example, ugma sa buntag kay maghimo ko ug projects or assignments tapos pagka hapon kay mag practice na ug sayaw and yells para sa girl scout” (IDI-01)

(Time management and it is important to set a schedule every day. For example, you have to do your projects and assignments in the morning and practice dancing in the afternoon)

Moreover, Ms. Cat (pseudonym) emphasizes the two key strategies which are prioritization and proactive scheduling to practice and enhance her productivity and reduce stress. By following scouting ideas that prioritize accountability, preparedness, and efficient use of time, this technique allows her to fully participate in scouting events while keeping a sufficient and balanced schedule. She indicated that:

“Gina una nako ug buhat ang mga naka priority. Kada adlaw ko ga set sa akong schedule para dili mag conflict akong oras ug mga buhatunon.” (IDI-06)

(I prefer to do first those in priority. I set and arrange my schedule every day so that I do not feel pressure and do not have any conflicts.)

Lastly, Ms. AJ (pseudonym) encapsulated the essence of effective time management in participating in scouting. It fosters a positive work-life balance, minimizing burnout and advancing mental wellness. She maintains a positive and sustainable lifestyle by making sure she doesn't excessive workload herself and that she makes time for relaxation and hobbies. She said that:

Naga butang ko ug schedule sa academics ug sa scouting kay para ma balanse ang duha ug wala koy mapabayaang nga buluhaton.” (FGD-06)

(I set a schedule for my academics and scouting so that both are balanced and I can neglect any workloads.)

Being Strong and Motivated

One of the foundations of fostering resilience in elementary school scouting programs is being strong and motivated. Even they encountered numerous challenges, from balancing school and scouting activities to managing other commitments. By fostering their strength and motivation, they can better navigate these difficulties. These experiences teach them to adapt and persevere in the face of difficulties. According to them, these strengths and motivation are crucial as they learn to overcome obstacles and stay focused on their goals. By embracing challenges, they develop problem-solving skills and a sense of accomplishment, which prepares them for future challenges.

Ms. Lovely (pseudonym), emphasized the importance of thinking positively, maintaining a cheerful attitude, and self-encouragement despite facing numerous challenges. Her mindset embodies strength and motivation as she chooses to focus on the solutions rather than problems. It was cited that;

“Always think positive, smile and always nako gina remind akong self nga kaya nako ni lagpasan despite sa kadaghang mga challenges” (IDI-01)

(I always think positively, smile, and always remind myself that I can do it despite of many challenges that we have.)

Additionally, Ms. Straight (pseudonym) mentioned the importance of praying as it reflects her reliance on spirituality or faith as a source of strength and guidance. Also, she has a full motivation that indicates her proactive mindset and determination to excel. In addition, she emphasizes how showing kindness to people, especially instructors and elders reveals her empathy, respect, and gratitude for those around her. She mentioned that:

“Pirmi ko mag pray ug ma motivate then always kind sa ubang tao labi na sa mga nakakatanda” (IDI-04)

(I always pray and stay motivated, then always kind to others especially to my teachers and to the elders.)

Furthermore, Ms. Kulot (pseudonym) mentioned the significance of being strong and motivated in all aspects of life. She maintains a cheerful demeanor which is always smiling and a grounded attitude to stay humble while facing challenges. Her approach to problems is proactive, instead of being deterred, she turns to prayer and self-motivation to tackle obstacles, embodying a determined and empowered mindset. She stated that:

“Mag smile and humble lang ko pirmi. Dili nako gina mind ang problema kay nahitabo naman, mag pray nalang ko kay God ug pirmi e motivate akong self nga kaya nako tanan” (IDI-05)

(I always smile and stay humble at all times. I did not mind any problem that we have instead, I always pray to God and I always motivate myself that I can do it all.)

Lastly, Mr. Slang (pseudonym) shared her experience as she fosters motivation and support by emphasizing the value of taking pleasure

in the moment while keeping a positive outlook with his group members. His dedication serves as an example that even in the hardships, he makes a way just to uplift and inspire his scouting friends. He indicated that:

“As being one of the motivations to my group, even from the one who struggles, I will lead them to be positive and motivated by just enjoying our life and always pray.” (FGD-04)

(As is one of the motivations to my group, even from the one who struggles, I will lead them to be positive and motivated by just enjoying our life and always praying)

Teamwork and Camaraderie

For elementary learners in scouting, teamwork and camaraderie play a crucial role as their coping mechanisms. Despite the demands of schoolwork, scouting activities, and other responsibilities, relying on the support and cooperation of their peers, they can navigate these challenges effectively. They believed that working together as a team fosters a sense of unity and shared purpose, while camaraderie provides emotional support and encouragement. Together, these elements help them to build resilience, enhance their problem-solving skills, and make their scouting experience more enjoyable and rewarding.

Mr. Slang (pseudonym) believed the idea of having a collaborative enjoyment process with his scouting friends is evidence of his joyful and positive outlook. He emphasizes that getting to know each other and working together reflects a deep appreciation for the synergy that comes from diverse perspectives and skills within a team. He values the learning experience derived from interacting with his fellow scouts, acknowledging that each member brings something unique. He indicated that:

“I feel happy and enjoy since we can finish our work earlier and getting to know each other to work together is better since we have learned a lot from each other.” (FGD-04)

(I feel happy and enjoy it since we can finish our work earlier and getting to know each other to work together is better since we’ve learned a lot from each other.)

Ms. Cat (pseudonym) highlighted the importance of collaboration and team support in fostering a positive and fulfilling experience with her scouting friends. Based on his experience we come up that she finds joy and a sense of being fortunate when surrounded by her friends because together they can support and assist each other in overcoming challenges and difficulties they encounter during their scouting activities. She stated that:

“Happy and blessed ko kung kauban nako akong mga friend’s kay magtinabangay mi para masulbad among mga problema” (IDI-06)

(I feel happy and blessed when I am with my friends because we can help each other to solve the problems that we have.)

Similarly, Ms. Lovely (pseudonym) learned that by embracing a positive and appreciative mindset, even the smallest moments and activities can bring happiness and satisfaction, especially in participating in scouting activities. She finds joy and fulfillment even in the little things in life, especially through the teamwork and camaraderie in scouting. She said that:

“The most interesting things nga akong natun-an kay you can freely enjoy your life bisan paman sa gamay nga butang” (IDI-01)

(The most interesting thing I have learned is that you can freely enjoy your life even with a small thing around.)

Ms. Pretty (pseudonym) highlighted the significance of having a strong relationship that they have with her friends. Emphasizing the comfort with which they can collaborate and support each other. The ability to freely ask each other shows the profound feeling of trust, teamwork, communication, and mutual respect among groups. She said that:

“Blessed ko kay naa sila, naa koy mapangayuan ug tabang ug dali ra namo ma sulbad ang mga problema.” (IDI-02)

(I’m so blessed with my friends because I can freely ask for help and we can easily solve our problems.)

In addition, Ms. Yeeshia (pseudonym) underscored the significance of feeling to be around her friends in the scouting community. She confidently shared that their friendships are strengthened and their overall scouting experience is improved by their ability to interact, communicate experiences, and have honest conversations about situations. This sense of unity creates a nurturing atmosphere in which they can grow as individuals, learn from one another, and conquer obstacles as a cohesive team. She indicated that:

“Para sa akua kay ma happy ko kay daghan nasad ko ug matun-an sa ilaha, maka bonding sad mi ug maka share² mi sa among mga problema.” (FGD-07)

(I am happy to be with my friends because I learned a lot from them, we can also bond and share our problems.)

Self-discipline and Goal Setting

In the formative years of elementary education, scouting programs offer a rich environment for children to cultivate essential life skills, one of these are self-discipline and goal setting. They believed that this would help them manage their experiences in scouting by providing them with practical tools to overcome challenges and stay focused. Also, they believe that self-discipline supports their

ability to adhere to the program’s structure and expectations, and goal setting offers a roadmap for achieving success and recognizing their achievements. This combination will enhance their overall experience, allowing them to fully participate in and benefit from the scouting programs.

Mr. Geyb (pseudonym) confidently confessed his techniques during their scout activities that highlight a practical approach to overcoming two distinct obstacles: financial shortages and punctuality issues. By consistently setting aside funds, he ensures that he has sufficient resources when needed, thereby mitigating the impact of financial limitations. Additionally, overcoming the challenges of punctuality, he adjusts his routine to ensure timely attendance and avoid negative outcomes. He said that:

“Base sa akong struggles nga kulang sa financial, akong techniques nga buhaton kay mag ipon ko sa akong alkansya para pag abot sa camporal kay naa nakoy pangbayad, naa pud koy isa ka struggle nga kung ma late kay punishan ka then para ma avoid nako ni nga situation kay magmata ko ug sayo para dili ko ma punishan. Atimanon nako ug tarong ang uban nga scouts para wala nay kagubot ug maghimo ko ug balaod para ma avoid ni nga problema.” (FGD-01)

(Based on my struggles with financial shortages, my techniques are to save money in my piggy bank so that by the time comes, I have enough to pay. I also have another struggle where being late results in a punishment. To avoid this situation, I wake up early so I won’t be punished.)

Ms. Lovely (pseudonym) echoed these sentiments and highlighted a comprehensive strategy for managing tasks and challenges. By combining resilience, organization, and prioritization, she effectively navigates her responsibilities, demonstrating a mature and thoughtful approach to personal and academic growth. This prioritization strategy helps her manage time effectively and ensures that important responsibilities are handled promptly. She confessed that:

“Akuang techniques kay bstay strong lang and mag set ug schedule sa mga buhatunon and mas unahon jud piri ang mga mas naka priority.” (IDI-02)

(My technique is to stay strong, set a schedule for tasks, and always prioritize the most important ones first)

Ms. Cat (pseudonym) illustrates a proactive approach to overcoming a common issue that reflects a clear understanding of how adjusting one’s routine can effectively address difficulties with waking up early. Her strategies reflect a thoughtful and self-aware approach to managing her time and improving her daily routines. By making incremental changes to her sleep habits, she demonstrates a commitment to overcoming personal challenges and enhancing their overall productivity and well-being. She said that:

“Since ang akong problem is magsayo ug mata. Then ang akong techniques kay mag practice ko nga sayo matulog pagka gabie ug magsayo ug mata buntag.” (IDI- 06)

(Since my problem is waking up early, my technique is to practice going to bed early at night and waking up early in the morning.)

Similarly, Mr. Slang (pseudonym) also reveals a strategic approach to his self-improvement and discipline. By recognizing the difficulty of waking up early and deciding to practice it regularly, coupled with morning exercise, he set a foundation for better physical and mental readiness. I believe that this kind of mindset is crucial in scouting, where early rising and physical fitness are often integral to participation and success. He said that:

For me to overcome my struggles which is hard to wake up in the morning then maybe, I will practice myself to wake up early and do an exercise.” (FGD-04)

(In order for me to overcome my struggles which is hard to wake up in the morning then maybe, I will practice myself to wake up early and do an exercise.)

Research Question No. 3: What are the insights that the learners can share to their co-students regarding scouting participation?

This question delved into the unique perspectives, observations, and understandings gained by the elementary learners regarding their participation in the scouting program. It sought to uncover the valuable insights, reflections, and lessons learned by the learners through their experiences in scouting. Also, the question aimed to understand the impact of scouting on personal growth, leadership development, teamwork, and character building. Additionally, this exploration seeks to highlight the potential for learners to inspire and empower their peers by sharing their unique perspectives and learnings from their scouting journey. The following themes were: being independent and responsible, social interaction and personal growth, learning fundamental life skills, and outdoor adventure and exploration.

Table 4. Insights of the Learners that They Can Share to Their Co-students Regarding Scouting Participation

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Being Independent and Responsible	“The effect of participating in scouting in my personal development is that being strong enough despite many challenges, being happy and not a lazy student in the future.” - IDI-04 “Through scouting, I know how to manage my responsibilities well and I train myself to work or do a task faster and being a responsible daughter” IDI-02

	<p>“Being a kind and loyal daughter. As an elementary student, we need to be independent person/child because not all the times that our parents are always there by our side” IDI-01</p> <p>“The values that I have learned in scouting are being kind, friendly, and being a trustworthy student. - IDI-03</p> <p>“Being helpful and we need to help our fellow students and even to the people who need help.” - FGD-01</p> <p>Being independent and we must know how to stand for our own so that we don’t rely too much on our parents” - FGD-02</p>
Social Interaction and Personal Growth	<p>“The values that I have learned is that I know how to solve small problems at school, being faithful to my parents, teachers and classmates and also being friendly to them” - IDI- 07</p> <p>“I learned how to cook rice and egg, and I know how to be responsible with my things and I learned to share my blessings with others and be close with other patrols” - FGD-07</p> <p>“I have enjoyed joining Boy Scouts since grade 1 because I have a fun competence against my friends due to the challenges and they will give their best along with me” - FGD-04</p> <p>“I love to explore and travel. For me, what made me feel interested to join scouting was being able to travel to other schools, and by that, I was able to discover many things around.”- IDI-02</p>
Learning Fundamental Life Skills	<p>“Self-motivation, being independent and cooking skills. Through participating in scouting activities, I learn how to cook simple dishes with the use of wood. Then I am independent enough when it comes to managing myself” - IDI-01</p> <p>“The skills that I have learned is leadership skills, through scouting I learned and know how to manage my group members for them to listen and cooperate well” FGD-04</p> <p>“Cooking skills and communication skills. Through scouting, I expose in any public places and I can’t feel ashamed anymore to the crowd” IDI- 03</p> <p>“The skills that I have learned are time management and leadership skills and being helpful to others.”- FGD-06</p> <p>“I learned cooking skills and self- motivation. Through scouting, I know how to cook simple dishes and I practice to motivate myself and to stand on my own.”- IDI-07</p>
Outdoor Adventure and Exploration	<p>“In scouting, you can learn a lot of skills and gain many benefits like being able to travel anywhere and meet a new friend. You can also try joining other activities that you might enjoy.” – FGD-02</p> <p>“From what I have experienced, I did not regret joining scouting activities because it is already a complete package. You can travel and discover new things at different schools.”– IDI- 06</p> <p>“It is a good choice to join scouting for you to train your mind and body depending on the challenges that will test your strength and weaknesses so that you can stand on your own and be an independent individual.”- FGD-01</p> <p>“In scouting, you will experience many things and enjoy yourself both physically and emotionally. Also, you can forget all your problems because you have a friend who will always help you.” – FGD-07</p>

Being Independent and Responsible

Being independent and responsible person are the essential qualities that elementary learners need to cultivate throughout their lives. Some of them said that when they engage in scouting activities, they embark on a transformative journey that hones their ability to navigate challenges, make decisions, and take ownership of their actions. Through the shared insights and experiences of the learners, they can be inspired their co-students embrace the values of independence and responsibility, unlocking a world of opportunities for self-discovery and leadership.

In fostering independence and responsibility, Ms. Straight (pseudonym) highlights the value of resilience and determination in the face of difficulties, emphasizing how scouting has given her the attitude and abilities necessary to face challenges directly. She also expresses a desire to keep a proactive and productive attitude, avoid laziness, and strive for happiness and fulfillment in her academic endeavors and beyond. She relates scouting participation to future achievement. She indicates that:

“Ang epekto sa scouting sa akola isip usa ka studyante kay maka kaya sa mga challenges bisan bata pa, dili dali maguol ug masakitan ug dili mahimong tamad nga studyante.” (IDI-04)

(The effect of participating in scouting in my personal development is being strong enough despite many challenges, being happy, and not a lazy student in the future.)

Ms. Pretty (pseudonym), also emphasized that her scouting experience has taught her effective time management and task prioritization, enabling her to handle her responsibilities effectively. Her insights emphasize the practical life skills and character development nurtured through scouting participation, which she believes can be shared with fellow learners to inspire similar growth and responsibility. She said that:

“Tungod sa scouting, kabalo nako mag manage sa akong mga buluhaton. Na train nako nga madali ang trabaho, Kinahanglan pinasapay ang lihok ug maging responsible nga anak” (IDI-02)

(Through scouting, I know how to manage my responsibilities well and I train myself to work or do a task faster and be a responsible daughter)

Also, Ms. Lovely (pseudonym) reflected a deep understanding of the values instilled by the elementary learners through scouting participation. She underscores the value of compassion and loyalty as characteristics of a responsible daughter and implies that scouting

has a beneficial impact on her character. She realizes that parents are not always around and that it is crucial for kids, even in primary school, to learn self-reliance and how to manage problems independently by highlighting the need for independence. She said that:

“Being kind and loyal daughter. Dapat dili ta magpabadlong sa mga parents. Then as elementary student, we need to be independent person kay dili sa tanan panahon naay mga parents sa atong tapad.” (IDI- 01)

(Being a kind and loyal daughter. As an elementary student, we need to be independent person/child because not all the time that our parents are always there by our side.)

Additionally, Mr. Handsome (pseudonym) underscored the values he has learned, which include kindness, friendliness, and being trustworthy as a student which support one's character growth, determination, and inner strength. His personal development is influenced by these values, which also benefit the scouting community and society as a whole. He indicated that:

Ang values nga akong natun an kay mahimong buotan, friendly ug masaligan nga bata. Kay sa girl scout matun an nimo ang magbinuotan ug masaligan.” (FGD-03)

(The values that I have learned in scouting are being kind, friendly, and a trustworthy student.)

Similarly, Mr. Geyb (pseudonym) shared his insights and emphasized the importance of being kind and supporting those in need as well as their peers. His dedication to helping others highlights the need for compassion, empathy, and community support in scouting. Furthermore, his acknowledgment of the importance of lending support to people in need demonstrates a motivated and caring mindset. These principles and deeds enhance the scouting experience while also fostering character development, personal growth, and constructive social change. He said that:

“Being helpful is a need. Tabangan nato ang mga kapwa studyante and even sa mga tao nga nanginahanglan ug tabang.” (FGD-01)

(Being helpful is a must and we need to help our fellow students and even the people who need help.)

Lastly, Ms. Happy (pseudonym) shared her insights about the significance of independence self-reliance, and a sense of responsibility. She emphasized the importance of being independent and not relying too much on parents or other people for help. Additionally, her understanding of the need to avoid an over-reliance on parents is a sign of a responsible and determined approach to developing into effective and independent adults. She said that:

“Para sa akoa is kanang being independent. We know how to stand for our self and para dili pud kaayo ta magsalig sa atong mga parents.” (FGD-02)

(For me is being independent and we must know how to stand on our own so that we don't rely too much on our parents)

Social Interaction and Personal Growth

Being involved in scouting especially the elementary learners is an essential journey that goes beyond outdoor experiences and skill-building exercises. Through scouting, these students go on a life-changing journey that develops crucial characteristics like resilience, empathy, teamwork, and leadership. As they participate in various activities, scouts learn to face challenges and adapt to new situations, fostering resilience that will serve them throughout their lives. They confidently shared that these will provide an opportunity for their self-development, allowing them to discover their strengths and interests. By trying new things, they gain a better understanding of themselves and their capabilities which helps them to set personal goals and strive for improvement, which builds their self-esteem and encourages a growth mindset.

According to the experiences shared by Ms. Rosas (pseudonym), she mentioned the ability to solve small problems at school, indicating that scouting has equipped her with problem-solving skills and a proactive approach to addressing challenges. Also, she addressed the importance of being faithful as the sign of having trust, respect, and loyalty, to have a healthy relationship and interaction with others. She mentioned that:

“Ang values nga akong natun-an kay kabalo nako magsulbad sa mga gamay nga problema sa school, maging faithful sa akong mga parents, teachers and classmates ug maging friendly pud sa ilaha” (IDI-07)

(The values that I have learned are that I know how to solve small problems at school, be faithful to my parents, teachers, and classmates, and also be friendly to them)

In addition, Ms. Monalisa (pseudonym) shared her experiences and explained how scouting has helped her develop a spirit of empathy and generosity by teaching her the importance of sharing her benefits with others. She also highlighted the value of building strong connections within her patrol, saying that scouting has assisted her in developing solid partnerships and fostering close relationships with her peers. She mentioned that:

“I learn how to cook rice and egg, and I know how to be responsible with my things and I learned to share my blessings to others and being close with other patrols” (FGD-07)

(I learned how to cook rice and eggs, and I know how to be responsible with my things and I learned to share my blessings with others and be close with other patrols)

Moreover, Mr. Slang (pseudonym) expressed his opinion that since elementary school, engaging in scouting activities has helped him grow personally and develop social skills. Since first grade, he has enjoyed being a Boy Scout, and he attributes his sense of competence to the difficulties he encounters in working with his friends to do with him. Thus, his idea suggests that scouting has not only given chances for personal growth but has also encouraged his fellow students to feel a sense of camaraderie and support from one another. He said that:

“I’ve enjoyed joining Boy Scouts since grade 1 because I have a fun competence against my friends due to the challenges and they will give their best along with me” (FGD-04)

(I’ve enjoyed joining Boy Scouts since grade 1 because I have fun competence against my friends due to the challenges and they will give their best along with me)

Lastly, Ms. Pretty (pseudonym) revealed her passion for travel and discovery and how these things affected her choice to become a scout. Her interest in employing scouting to visit other schools suggested that she is looking for fresh experiences, educational opportunities, and exposure to various settings. Her curiosity and need to learn new things help her grow personally by broadening her horizons and enhancing her abilities. Furthermore, her statement that she learned a lot while touring points to the growth of social contact in scouting. She pointed that:

“Hilig ko mag explore and mag travel so para sa ako ang nakahatag ug interest sa scouting is maka travel sa ubang school and tungod ana is daghan ko ug ma discover nga lain laing butang from others.” (IDI-02)

(I love to explore and travel. For me, what made me feel interested in joining scouting was being able to travel to other schools and by that, I was able to discover many things around)

Learning Fundamental Life Skills

Scouting is not just simply enjoying the great outdoors but also learning fundamental life skills. Based on the different insights that I collected during our interview session, through engaging activities, leadership opportunities, and hands-on learning experiences, scouting teaches learners practical abilities and personal qualities that extend well beyond the scouting program. By sharing their personal experiences, realization, and insights, some of them believed in the essence of different skills that they have learned in scouting. From self-discipline, being an independent and responsible individual, cooking skills, leadership skills, and communication skills, they can demonstrate to their co-students how scouting equips and molds them with the tools necessary for navigating life’s challenges.

Ms. Lovely (pseudonym) highlighted the multifaceted benefits of scouting participation, including self-motivation, independence, and practical skills development. By sharing her experiences with her co-students, she encouraged a culture of personal growth, resilience, and self-reliance within the scouting community. She shared that:

“Mag motivate sa self, maging independent and cooking skills kay tungod sa scouting kabalo nako mag luto ug mga simple nga lutuonon gamit ang kahoy, then kabalo nako mag manage sa akong sarili” (IDI-01)

(Self-motivation, being independence, and cooking skills. Through participating in scouting activities, I learn how to cook simple dishes with the use of wood. Then I am independent enough when it comes to managing myself)

Mr. Geyb (pseudonym) emphasized how scouting engagement may have an enormously beneficial impact on the development of skills and self-confidence, especially in the area of leadership. He helps to foster a culture of leadership, teamwork, and personal development within the scouting community by sharing her experiences and lessons learned with her fellow students. This encourages others to take the initiative, lead with confidence, and positively impact both their own lives and the lives of those around them. He stated that:

“Ang skills nga akong natun-an kay leadership skills, kay tungod sa scouting natun-an nako unsaon pag manage sa akong mga kauban nga maminaw sila sa akoa ug mag cooperate” (FGD-01)

(The skills that I have learned are leadership skills, through scouting I learned and know how to manage my group members so they to listen and cooperate well.)

Ms. Polka (pseudonym) Foster how scouting takes a comprehensive approach to building self-confidence and skills, such as the capacity to cook, communicate, and shift within public places without feeling nervous. She promoted a culture of development, self-empowerment, and discovery within the scouting community by sharing her experiences with her fellow pupils, encouraging them to take on new challenges, develop their talents, and succeed with confidence. She stated that:

“Cooking skills ug kanang mag communicate sa uban kay tungod sa girl scout dili nako maulaw ug na expose nako sa ilaha” (IDI-03)

(Cooking skills and communication skills. Through scouting, I am exposed to public places, and I cannot feel ashamed anymore of the crowd)

Ms. AJ (pseudonym) candidly shared her insights about the importance of time management, kindness, and leadership not only scouting specific ideas; these are lifelong values that mold her into a responsible and compassionate individual. She is very appreciative of the life-changing opportunities scouting has given to her, and she is looking forward to carrying on their group's growth and service endeavors. She said that:

“Ang skills nga akong nabal-an kay time management ug pag lead sa grupo the kana pud unsaon pag tabang sa uban.” (FGD-06)

(The skills that I have learned are time management and leadership skills and being helpful to others.)

In addition, Ms. Monalisa (pseudonym) mentioned that through scouting, she has learned how to cook simple dishes and has also practiced motivating herself to stand independently. She also revealed that scouting has helped her develop her practical abilities, like cooking, but it also encouraged her personal development by encouraging independence and self-motivation. These experiences frequently develop the foundation of scouting's objective, which is to create well-rounded people who can overcome obstacles and positively impact their communities. She indicated that:

“Ang natun an nako kay cooking skills kabalo nako magluto ug simple nga lutuonon ug ma practice na nako akong sarili nga e motivate ug mo barog sa sarili nga paa.” (IDI-07)

(I learned cooking skills and self-motivation. Through scouting, I know how to cook simple dishes, and I practice to motivate myself and to stand on my own.)

Outdoor Adventure and Exploration

Scouting offers a unique blend of outdoor adventure, learning, and exploration. Here are some insights based on the personal experiences of my participants that can be shared with their fellow students. First is making new friends and building a sense of community wherein working together on different activities, sharing ideas and experiences, and overcoming challenges together will create a strong bond. Second, is a deep connection with nature where they can travel around and explore things that they never experience since then. Lastly is personal growth and development where they can learn, heal, and enjoy their selves both physically and emotionally.

Ms. Happy (pseudonym) emphasized that scouting is an incredible opportunity to learn new skills, travel to exciting places, and make lasting friendships. By sharing her experiences, she hopes to inspire more students to join scouting and discover the numerous benefits it offers. Also, she believed that scouting not only enhances personal development but also creates a sense of community and adventure that is truly rewarding. She said that:

“Sa scouting daghan kayo ka ug matun-an nga mga skills ug daghan pud kag ma benefits like maka travel ta bisag asa ug maka meet ug mga new friends. Maka try pud ka ug apil sa uban pang activities nga maganahan ta.” (FGD-02)

(In scouting, you can learn a lot of skills and gain many benefits like being able to travel anywhere and meet a new friend. You can also try joining other activities that you might enjoy.)

Similarly, Ms. Cat (pseudonym) shared her thoughts and experiences during her scouting participation. She expressed confidently that joining scouting is an experience she wholeheartedly recommends. According to her, it's a complete package that offers travel, discovery, friendships, and personal growth. She believed that scouting often takes her to various schools, campsites, and even different cities.

Each trip is an adventure where she gets to explore new environments, cultures, and communities. She said that:

“Sama sa akong naagian, dili jud ka magmahay kung muapil ug scouting kay package na siya, maka travel ug maka discover ka ug mga new things sa lain-lain mga schools.” (IDI-06)

(From what I have experienced, I do not regret joining scouting activities because it is already a complete package. You can travel and discover new things at different schools.)

Additionally, Mr. Slang (pseudonym) highlighted the significance of scouting in our personal growth. According to him, joining scouting is an excellent choice for training both your mind and body. The challenges you face will test your strengths and weaknesses, helping you grow into a capable and independent individual. He believes that recognizing our strengths helps us to grow and those weaknesses allow us to focus on improving it, ultimately making a more effective and growth mindset. He said that:

“It is a good choice to join scouting for you to train your mind and body depending on the challenges that will test your strength and weaknesses so that you can stand on your own and be an independent individual.” (FGD-04)

(It is a good choice to join scouting for you to train your mind and body depending on the challenges that will test your strengths and weaknesses so that you can stand on your own and be an independent individual.)

Moreover, Ms. Monalisa (pseudonym) highlighted the unique benefits that scouting may offer which is the wealth of experiences and emotional fulfillment. She thought that the physical enjoyment of scouting not only improves our fitness but boosts our energy and

enthusiasm. Also, it's not just about physical activities but also nurtures our emotional well-being, wherein scouting provides a break from the stresses of daily life. Being outdoors, engaging in activities you love, and spending time with friends can be a great way to relax and recharge. She said that:

“Daghan ug ma experience sa scouting ug ma enjoy nimo imong self physically and emotionally, sa scouting sad kay malimtan nimo imong ga problema kay naay mga friends nga always ka tabangan.” (FGD-07)

(In scouting, you will experience many things and enjoy yourself both physically and emotionally. Also, you can forget all your problems because you have a friend who will always help you.)

Conclusions

The results of this phenomenological study provided an opportunity to explore and comprehend the real-life experiences, challenges, coping strategies, and valuable insights of elementary learners in the context of scouting. With this gathered information, it was crucial to consider the implications it holds for enhancing the scouting experiences and meeting the different needs of the elementary learners as they were undergoing scouting participation.

The revelation that elementary learners experience difficulties in financial support or assistance carried significant meaning. This suggested that these elementary learners are battling with a lack of finances to support their needs and other fees related to their participating in scouting activities. The implications for these findings suggested that the Department of Education and other personnel should provide enough funds, enough time, skilled personnel, and motivation to enhance the effective participation of scouting in elementary years.

Moreover, the elementary learners may use the coping strategies shared by the participants including having a mindset of being strong and motivated in their participating scouting activities, especially when they encounter different challenges in life, also they mentioned always praying with our almighty God to ask for guidance and comfort. This strategy may equip the mindset of elementary learners to face life's obstacles with courage, perseverance, and a sense of purpose by developing resilience, a growth mentality, and a supportive community.

Additionally, the findings that emphasized the importance of continuous scouting programs as one of the educational outdoors for elementary students have significant implications in different primary schools in the Davao region. It means that the scouting program offers a multifaceted approach to education that encompasses character development, leadership skills, environmental awareness, social understanding, and health benefits. By embracing scouting as an integral part of their educational journey, students in Davao not only gain valuable life skills but also become empowered individuals ready to make a positive impact on their communities and the world at large.

Lastly, future researchers are interested in studying the lived experiences of elementary learners during their participating scouting program. This study may provide valuable assistance in gathering necessary information for their research. The findings, review of related literature, and methodology employed in this study may serve as important references for their research papers.

Implication for Further Research

This study included a sample of fourteen (14) participants who were actively participating in scouting activities for almost 1-3 years. It is important to note that the selection of participants was selected for the specific context, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to the other settings. The results can be limited statistically, which would weaken the overall research. When analyzing the results, it is crucial to consider these limitations and to acknowledge that higher sample sizes will be required in future research to guarantee a deeper comprehension of the phenomenon.

Through the use of a phenomenological approach, the researcher was able to identify the fundamental themes and structures that define the event being investigated. The researcher suggested that narrative research focuses on comprehending people's stories, experiences, and perspectives through the lens of storytelling. By capturing the personal experiences of elementary learners, this approach might enable a comprehensive examination of their distinct experiences, difficulties, and development as primary students. It may also provide an opportunity to uncover the contextual factors and emotions. The implementation of narrative research allows for a deeper comprehension of the variety of issues faced by elementary school pupils in the context of scouting, offering insightful information that can motivate their fellow students to participate in scouting programs.

Lastly, a potential avenue for future research is to conduct a comprehensive analysis to explore the specific needs and challenges faced by the elementary learners during their participating scouting for almost 1-3 years in the program. This in-depth investigation could identify critical areas as well as the benefits where support and motivation are necessary to engage and enhance their personal growth as they explore different scouting activities. By gaining a deeper understanding of their experiences and addressing their individual needs, this research has the potential to better prepare and empower the learners, ultimately leading to improvement in the ways of scouting activities that help learners to motivate and encourage them to join.

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